

EDUCATIONAL PROGRAM USING MANADO LANGUAGE VIDEOS AND SONGS AS EFFORTS TO INCREASE CHILDREN'S KNOWLEDGE AND ATTITUDES ABOUT ANTICIPATING SEXUAL ABUSE

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Abstract

The latest data in Indonesia shows an increasing incidence of child sexual abuse in the last decade. The impact of sexual abuse can cause developmental disorders due to psychological trauma such as shame, fear, depression and physical injury, pain and infection. So far, the preventive effort from sexual crimes in elementary schools is by providing education, which generally uses leaflet media. This study aims to determine the effectiveness of educational programs using the Manado language video song on the knowledge and attitudes of school age children in anticipating sexual abuse. The research design was a quasi experiment pre-post test nonequivalent control group with an educational program in the intervention group using videos and songs in Manado with 36 respondents and 36 respondents in the control group using leaflet media. Measurement of knowledge and attitudes using a questionnaire. The results showed that there were differences in the mean knowledge and attitudes of school-age children who were given an educational program about anticipating sexual abuse using the Manado language song video, which was higher and significantly different when compared to the mean knowledge and attitudes of school-age children after being given an educational program using leaflets (p value = 0.000 at $\alpha = 0.05$). The use of educational videos and songs in Manado is recommended to increase children's motivation and interest in learning so that they can increase children's knowledge and attitudes.

Keywords: Educational, Videos and Songs Language in Manado, Knowledge and Attitudes, Children.

INTRODUCTION

Sexual abuse is a type of mistreatment of children (child abuse). Mistreatment of children is by involving children in sexual activities that they themselves do not understand because the child's development has not reached that stage. Moreover, they have not been equipped with knowledge about sex education and reproductive health (Hockenberry & Wilson, 2015).

In Indonesia, the Child Protection Law has existed since 2002. However, the latest data shows that the incidence of sexual abuse has increased in the last decade. In 2016, sexual abuse ranked first among several types of violence against children, namely 5066 cases (35%), where the most incidence in girls was 4483 cases (SIMFONI-KPPPA, 2016). The results of the 2018 National Survey on the Life Experience of Children and Adolescents in Indonesia, conducted by the Ministry of Women's Empowerment and Child Protection (KPPPA), show that 1 in 11 girls and 1 in 17 boys have experienced sexual violence. In North Sulawesi Province, cases of violence against children in 2018 amounted to 125 cases, while in 2019 it increased to 150 cases. Of these, sexual violence ranks 1st with 47 cases (Integrated Service Center for the Protection of Women and Children/P2TP2A of the North Sulawesi PPPAD Office, 2020).

According to the Ministry of PPPA (2016), the most cases of sexual abuse are in the age group of 6-12 years (33%). Osmanoglu's (2019) research, on 616 students aged 7-14 years noted that around 70% of violence against children occurred in the young group of children in the range of 9-11 years. Most perpetrators are adults or adolescents who have known the child or have power over the child such as parents, siblings, teachers, friends, neighbors and other people who have access to the child or his own playmates.

The impact of sexual abuse can cause developmental delays in children due to psychological trauma such as shame, fear, depression coupled with physical trauma such as injuries, pain and infections (Wong, Hokenberry-Eaton, Wilson, Winkelstein, & Schwartz, 2009).

One of the efforts taken by the government to reduce the number of sexual violence cases is by socializing to all elements of society so that they can play an active role so that children are protected from violence. So far, preventive efforts to protect children from sexual crimes in elementary schools are by providing sex education. In general, sex education in elementary schools uses standard methods with leaflet media.

According to their growth and development, elementary school children have characteristics that are often easier for sexual abuse perpetrators to deceive them. According to Piaget, the cognitive development of school-age children is in the conservation stage, where children are increasingly thinking logically and are able to classify, organize, organize and sort facts to solve problems. School-age children begin to think inductively, by no longer being self-centered and able to consider things from the perspective of others but do not yet have the ability to face something abstract and solve problems concretely based on what they feel. (Wong, et al. 2009). Therefore, it is necessary to provide information through interactive education that can attract interest in learning according to the stage of school-age children, including using songs and movements through videos.

The purpose of this study is to determine the effectiveness of educational programs using Manado language song videos on the knowledge and attitudes of school-age children in anticipating sexual abuse.

METHODS

This study uses a quasi-experiment pre-post test nonequivalent control group design. The sample was taken by purposive sampling technique, namely school age children 9-12 years old (grades 5-6) as many as 36 respondents in SD GMIM IV as the intervention group and 36 respondents in SD GMIM VII as the control group. The intervention provided was in the form of an educational program on anticipating sexual abuse in the form of a video which also contained songs in Manado (regional) language, while in the control group, education was carried out using leaflet media.

The research was carried out in July-October 2020. The instrument used to measure children's knowledge and attitudes is a questionnaire. The knowledge questionnaire consisted of 18 questions with a score range of 2-36 and the attitude questionnaire consisted of 12 questions using a likert scale with a score range of 12-60. The questionnaire contains ways to prevent sexual abuse such as; 4 private areas that should not be touched by others, what conditions and who are allowed to touch, perpetrators of sexual abuse and efforts to prevent sexual abuse. The validity test of

the instrument used the Pearson Correlation Product Moment technique. The value of probability (sig.2 tail) in the validity test of 30 items was obtained with an $> r$ value from the table r value of 0.514 (15 respondents) and had a positive significance value of $< \alpha = 0.05$. Meanwhile, the reliability test showed that the Alpha Cronbach value was $>$ from the r -value of the table, 0.749 knowledge and 0.617 attitude.

The education program lasts for 30 minutes, carried out 3 times with an interval of 1-2 days, preceded by a pretest and posttest given 2 days after the 3rd education. The education program is carried out while still paying attention to Covid-19 prevention protocols during the pandemic such as measuring body temperature, washing hands/using hand sanitizer, physical distancing and using Personal Protective Equipment/PPE such as masks and face shields).

In this study, it still considers the principles of research ethics such as respect for human dignity, beneficence and justice (Polit & Beck, 2012), and has gone through an ethical review from the Health Research Ethics Commission (KEPK) of the Manado Ministry of Health Polytechnic in 2020.

RESULT & DISCUSSION

1. Characteristics Responden

The characteristics of the respondents can be seen in the following table 1.

Table 1: Respondent characteristics based on age, number of siblings and gender

Variable	Intervention Groups		Control Group		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Age						
9	4	11.11	3	8.33	7	9.72
10	10	27.78	12	33.33	22	30.56
11	16	44.44	14	38.90	30	41.67
12	6	16.67	7	19.44	13	18.05
Number of Siblings						
1	2	5.56	2	5.56	4	5.56
2	7	19.44	6	16.66	13	18.06
3	15	41.67	14	38.89	29	40.27
4	7	19.44	9	25.00	16	22.22
5	3	8.33	3	8.33	6	8.33
6	2	5.56	2	5.56	4	5.56
Gender						
Male	19	52.78	18	50.00	38	51.39
Female	17	47.22	18	50.00	35	48.61

The data on the characteristics of the respondents in table 1 above showed that the age of the respondents was more than 11 years (41.67%) and few respondents were 9 years old (9.72%). The gender of respondents was almost equal in girls (48.61) and boys (51.39). The characteristics of the largest number of siblings were 3 people (40.27%), and few respondents had 1 person and 6 brothers respectively at 5.56%.

2. Analysis of Average Differences in Knowledge and Attitudes

The data normality test using the Kolmogorof-Smirnov test obtained results, namely both pretest and posttest data on the variables of knowledge and attitude were normally distributed (p value > 0.05). Meanwhile, the data homogeneity test uses

Levene's test on knowledge and attitude pretest data, which can be seen in the following table.

Table 2: Analysis of Pretest Data Homogeneity Test of Knowledge and Attitude Variables in the Intervention Group and Control Group

Variable	N	Mean	SD	Min-Max	P Value
Knowledge					0.413
Intervention	36	9.11	1.545	6-12	
Control	36	8.81	1.600	6-11	
Attitude					0.496
Intervention	36	42.03	2.952	36-47	
Control	36	42.56	5.369	38-57	

The results of the data homogeneity test are shown in table 2. The above shows the pretest score of the respondents' knowledge and attitude in the intervention group and the control group, obtained a p value of > 0.05 . The assumption obtained from the results of this test is that the intervention group has the same pretest data knowledge and attitude with the control group.

Table 3: Analysis of Differences in Average Knowledge and Attitudes After the Education Program (Posttest) in the Intervention Group and Control Group

Variable	N	Mean	Min-Max	SD	SE	P Value
Knowledge						0.000
Intervention	36	15.50	12-18	1.797	0.299	
Control	36	10.11	7-14	1.617	0.270	
Attitude						0.000
Intervention	36	55.53	49-60	3.273	0.546	
Control	36	49.06	38-57	4.635	0.772	

The results of the statistical test in table 3 above showed that the average posttest score of knowledge in the intervention group and the control group was significantly different with a p value of 0.000 (< 0.05). Likewise, the average posttest score of attitudes in the intervention group and the control group differed significantly with a p value of 0.000 (< 0.05). Thus, the assumption from the results of this test is that there is a significant influence of educational programs using videos of Manado language songs on the knowledge and attitudes of school-age children.

3. Discussion

The increase in sexual abuse cases from year to year has attracted serious attention from various parties to make efforts to protect children. According to UNICEF (2015), the occurrence of sexual abuse in children is due to individual factors, including lack of education and attitudes supportive of sexual violence. Providing education in educational institutions is one of the preventive efforts carried out to prevent violence against children, including sexual abuse. In fact, in Permenkes PPPA no. 6 of 2011, article 9 instructs that this education can be carried out by integrating through relevant subjects and extracurricular activities, including in the curriculum at the Basic Education level.

Sexual education programs for school children are usually carried out for school-age children before puberty. This program provides information about the function of the body's reproductive organs, including responsibility for the sexual organs. Exposure to this information is influenced by the active role of various parties, including; parents

and the school (James Nelson, & Aswill 2013). Lack of information about this can lead to a decrease in a child's defenses against the risk of sexual abuse.

The occurrence of an optimal learning process in educational programs requires supporting components, including the use of effective learning media as a conductor of information, especially since the media is a media that students like such as videos (Hadi, 2017). The results of the analysis in this study found that video learning media is more effective in increasing knowledge and attitudes compared to conventional educational programs using leaflet media. This is in line with several studies that report video as an effective learning medium. Research by Vidayanti, Tungkaki, Retnaningsih (2020) on the use of animated videos in 36 school-age children in sex education at SDN Mustokorejo Yogyakarta, found that the use of this media was effective (p value 0.000) could increase the knowledge of school-age children. Research by Solehati, Kosasih, Lukman (2019) on Health Education "Healthy Breakfast" using video media in 323 students in grades 4-6 of SDN Leuwi Bandung, found that there was a significant influence of the use of video media on knowledge (p value < 0.000) and children's attitudes (p value < 0.000). The average increase in children's knowledge from 78.0% to 95.0% and attitude from 79.3% to 97.8%.

Along with the development of multimedia learning, video as an audiovisual media, has recently been developed using other learning media so that the use of various senses in the learning process is maximized, so that information in learning is easier to absorb (Hadi, 2017). According to Notoatmodjo (2011), seeing and hearing activities contribute greatly to the increase in a person's knowledge when compared to the use of only one sense. The use of songs as a learning medium is an interactive method that uses these two senses.

The use of songs in learning has been developed in several studies. A 2016 study by Aguire, Bustinza & Garvich on 56 children in primary schools in Peru, reported that the use of songs in the learning process can increase children's motivation to learn English lessons. Children show a great desire to participate in this lesson both in taking the initiative to learn, often asking questions about the topics discussed and looking happy when doing activities in class because the classroom environment becomes positive and cheerful when compared to a class without music.

The use of songs for children should have lyrics that are not difficult, use simple and easy-to-understand words so that the message or information to be conveyed can be well received. Mother tongue is the first language that can be accepted by children naturally. The mother tongue can be a regional language obtained from the family. In North Sulawesi Province, the mother tongue that is often used is Manado. Therefore, school-age children who are still in the stage of growth and development, must be strengthened through language (Ibda, 2017).

Several studies that strengthen the use of songs in education can improve children's knowledge and attitudes, including; research: Wardhani & Budiono (2018). Their research was conducted on 62 elementary school children in the city of Semarang, which found that the use of songs in nutrition education can effectively increase children's knowledge about vegetable and fruit consumption. Likewise, the research of Al-efeshat & Baniabdelrahman (2020) in Jordan, obtained the results that the use of songs in English learning can increase children's good attitudes in the learning process where children show seriousness and perseverance in learning. Research in line with this technique was conducted in southern Africa by Anderson et al. (2018).

The high incidence and mortality of malaria in children gave researchers the idea to use songs to educate children about how malaria is transmitted and recognize the early symptoms of malaria. The results of the study show that the use of this song can help children better understand how to protect themselves from the dangers of malaria mosquitoes.

CONCLUSION

The difference in the average knowledge and attitude of school-age children who were given an educational program on anticipating sexual abuse using a video of a Manado song was higher and significantly different when compared to the average knowledge and attitude of school-age children after being given an educational program using a leaflet (p value = 0.000 on $\alpha = 0.05$).

Education to children about anticipating sexual abuse should be carried out continuously and programmatically using interactive media. The use of educational videos and Manado language songs is recommended to increase children's motivation and interest in learning so that they can increase children's knowledge and attitudes.

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